

Multidisciplinary Approach in Arts, Science and Commerce

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Abstract-

Multidisciplinary Approach for Arts, Science and Commerce is represented as methods, way, policies, techniques, rules and regulation in the foundation and successful functioning of the Education, Learning and Research work in the management of the three different streams of Departments those are Arts, Science and Commerce. Then Technology is a important thing in the Educational system and the foundation and establishment made under UGC Union Grants Commission is important the laws that has been enforced by the government of India.

Keywords- Multidisciplinary Approach, Arts-Science-Commerce, Education-Learning-Research, PHD.

Methodologies-

The use of different questionnaires, survey, graphs, pie-charts Research, Experiments, Models and Projects, Examinations, Mcqs and Quizzes.

Objectives-

The introduction to Modern Technology of Learning. Today's modern techniques plays role of building the base through bookish language but also from Technology. Technology plays a major role in the foundation of the Teaching Career subject like B.Ed Bachelors in Education. The education that runs according to these three streams. In schools and Colleges the study of Arts. Science and Commerce is compulsory. For all age group students the studying of these streams is mandatory till class Ten then after that you can change your stream according to your academic score after giving secondary examination you are eligible for College. The education should be considered compulsory and the choice of the subject should be merely based on marks and grades. Any University Or Council Board should strictly check upon the performance and the eligibility. New syllabus should be introduced when it becomes backdated.

Then Internet should be used for Research Work. In the Classroom method of Teaching the classes should be interactive. There should be no unfair means, injustice or malpractices during any kind of examinations.

Introduction-

Multidisciplinary Approach in Arts, Science and Commerce. Multidisciplinary which talks about the various streams of Education and Learning, Arts, Science and Commerce these are the different streams and the method of learning takes place is a question because there should be a proper functioning in the teaching of Arts, Commerce and Science. In these three streams without basic learning and Teaching Method these three departments are incomplete. What do you understand by Arts, Science and Commerce are these just streams of learning. No it is connected to real life and the study of these streams is

compulsory because it solves real life problem makes a person educated for not only Teaching but also for Challenges to know what is unfamiliar and to know what is unknown. Education makes a person fully established, personality wise, wisdom and knowledge and a better human being or say literate and a learned person in different fields and sectors of life. Arts Department for higher Education it is designated as Bachelors of Arts, Bachelors of Science and Bachelors of Commerce. The study materials are hectic but valuable. Arts stream consists of History Geography, Psychology, Political Science, Social Science and Sociology. Then Science streams consist of Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Geology, Engineering, Medical Science. The Commerce stream consists of Accounts, Finance, Business Studies, Economics and Maths. English, Computer Science, Environmental Education and Moral Science, 2nd Language and 3rd Language are compulsory subjects. Masters is for Highest achievement in the Educational Qualification System. The education is becoming more and more complex and hard due to the growth of advancement.

Advantages for The Multidisciplinary Approach-

Today's modern techniques play a vast role in the career opportunities. The best way to make a student understand is through Technology demonstration. There are various short term and long term courses that are important and are being introduced to make a student thorough with the streams of Education which is Arts, Science and Commerce. Then use of Technology is not only important for the lectures but also for the use in the examinations especially for Competitive Examinations. Then mock tests, quizzes which makes the preparation for the examinations a lot more easier. The genuine platforms like Unacademy where all courses or for example various Online Universities which provides with free courses where the lecturers makes things easier for the students to understand and the students

become thorough with the syllabus. Along with study, practice is also compulsory.

Disadvantages For The Multidisciplinary Approach

Then as you know that there are differences between the streams. In Arts department there is a lot of subjects to memorize, in Science where you need to use your intellect, practice and learn where as in Commerce you need to understand and practice a lot especially all mathematics problems which need to be solved. Not only in examination but also in the real life challenges in a job post. Computer which is a must and important subject there is a trend of having online classes. Online classes are beneficial but regular classes are important for Education. Like for example to give attention to each and every student during online classes. But if there is any kind of Research Work Or presentation or professional meetings then Online Classes are very good and helpful. But for juniors when there is the learning stage it becomes very difficult to manage every one in an online session. There are so many websites that are launching various educational platforms and facilities for the students of any stream but there are frauds as well investment should be checked upon. PHD is the final stage of an entire Education System there are so many drawbacks in pursuing it and there are no limitations and boundaries that you can research according to your chosen stream and Department. There are very few who cope up with the thesis part. The lengthy and long papers after paper is a part of Research work which are given to PHD students. The student faces a lot of problems like health problems, stress, tension, and waking up nights after nights to submit Research papers are so much burdensome. Have to complete Thesis writing otherwise your PHD will remain incomplete.

Suggestions-

PHD is not that important you can continue later on when there is a lot of free time. Then you can apply for different posts like Assistant Professor and Senior Research Assistant. Then a lot of other posts like Civil Engineering and Mechanical Engineering. Then a lot more other opportunities are there for the Department you have chosen for. UGC has taken into consideration and other Government related Online Universities such as IGNOU, MOOC, SWAYAM to give education and also government jobs. There are also free online courses available. If you want to become a Researcher or you want to opt for any kind of job related courses or educational courses you will find here. There are too many courses listed in their website portals where you can apply for. The admission the examination are held all Nationally and is recognized globally and

courses will be helpful in your competitive examinations.

Conclusions-

The Multidisciplinary Approach in Arts, Science and Commerce can be done through seminars and webinars and also many ways as stated above. Syllabus of various subjects should be completed by the School and University Teachers but in Higher Education it becomes impossible so notes should be provided. Psychology which should be made compulsory subject for all streams and departments. And Degree Certificates and Award are given on Completion of various subjects after any Board Examinations And University Examinations. And not being able to complete any degree such as Graduations and Post Graduations which will result as an incomplete degree no Degree will be provided. Then there are various examination rules and regulations which are enforced by the State Government Or a National Government should be practice sincerely regarding failing and passing, giving supplementary examinations and rechecking examination papers are given equal rights for every student.

References-

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